

**Study of Multimedia usage among undergraduate teachers with reference to
Technological Acceptance Model**

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Abstract:

In today's world, teaching is incomplete without the use of multimedia which includes power point presentations, projectors, education software's, interactive software's, animation. With multimedia teaching becomes fun and experiential for students, however because of resources limitation of educational institutions this is difficult to implement in all educational institutions. In this study the major measured attitude variables are perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and intention to use. There samples taken here are 168 teachers employed in private and government colleges in Bengaluru Rural. Convenience based sampling method is used here. The outcome of the study found to influence the intention to use of multimedia if the multimedia materials are easy to use having relevance to self-learning, regional language use, user friendliness in accessing the functionalities.

Keywords —Multimedia, undergraduate teachers, TAM, Technological Acceptance Model, Intention to use multimedia.

Introduction

Multimedia is a term that refers to a collection of elements such as text, graphics, animation, audio, and video that encompasses everything we see and hear in our daily lives (Vaughan, 2006). Multimedia applications can be used in a variety of settings, including education, business, residences, and public spaces. This article discusses educational multimedia applications. Texts, images, audios, videos, animations, and user control are the six primary elements of multimedia applications for educational purposes. Additionally, this article discusses the benefits and drawbacks of multimedia applications in education. There are also a few characteristics in education that are worth noting, including screen design, interaction and feedback, navigation, and video and audio elements. Multimedia applications are used in

education as a source of information to deliver educational resources to students. Multimedia applications are also used to enhance the learning process and increase student-teacher or lecturer interaction. Teachers or lecturers can enhance the learning experience by incorporating multimedia applications. Rather than writing on the white board, a multimedia application can highlight certain critical points. There is no doubt about the educational value of multimedia applications. This new context for learning will undoubtedly have an effect on how teachers or lecturers teach and how students learn. They are constantly on the lookout for more effective ways to engage students during the learning process and to improve student learning outcomes.

According to research, when abstract, new, and novel concepts are presented verbally and visually, people learn them more easily (Salomon, 1979). Additionally, empirical research indicates that visual media make concepts more accessible to individuals than text media and aid in subsequent recall (Cowen, 1984). Willingham's (2009) research begins with a straightforward question: "Why do students retain everything they see on television but forget what we lecture?" — because visual media aids in the retention of concepts and ideas by students. Bransford, Browning, and Cocking (1999, p 194) also emphasize the critical role of technology in extending the possibilities of one-way communication media such as movies, documentaries, television shows, and music into new areas that require interactive learning, such as visualizations and student-created content.

In this study, Technological Acceptance Model was classified into four dimensions in this study: perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, attitude toward use, and intention to use, as illustrated in figure. This is the base of research framework in this study.

Figure1: Framework towards Research

In this study, a questionnaire survey was used to ascertain undergraduate college teachers' acceptance of integrated multimedia teaching materials in Bengaluru. Each questionnaire item was graded on a five-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree." The survey instrument includes four items assessing perceived ease of use, four items assessing perceived usefulness, four items assessing attitude toward use, and five items assessing intention to use. The following factors were evaluated in the study: Perceived Usefulness, perceived ease of use, Attitude toward using, Intention to use. According to TAM theory, this study examined all variables affecting teachers' acceptance of integrated multimedia teaching materials instruction for undergraduate students in Bengaluru Rural.

This study examines the intention to use of multimedia if the multimedia materials are easy to use having relevance to self-learning, regional language use, user friendliness in accessing the functionalities.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data analysis was conducted in a Three-stage process. First, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was performed to confirm the findings. Reliability and validity test was done on the model followed by Structural Equation Model (SEM). SPSS Statistics 25.0 software is used factor analysis. SPSS Amos 22.0 software is used for CFA model fit and SEM to estimate the relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variable so as to accept or reject the hypothesis.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA):

Confirmation Factor Analysis explains the extent the observed variables are linked to the latent factors in the research. CFA postulates the relations between the variables based on the theory, empirical research or both and then test the hypothesized structure statistically. In this study the model is developed based on priori subject and CFA is used to confirm it.

Figure2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA):

The measurement model represents the pattern in which each measure loads on a particular factor. It represents how the measured variables come together to represent construct and is used for validation and reliability checks.

Table1: Covariance between the Latent variables:

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
PEOU1	<---	PEOU	1.000			
PEOU2	<---	PEOU	1.067	.062	17.120	***
PEOU3	<---	PEOU	1.051	.061	17.352	***
PEOU4	<---	PEOU	1.078	.061	17.688	***
PU1	<---	PU	1.000			
PU2	<---	PU	1.020	.063	16.188	***
PU3	<---	PU	.972	.067	14.585	***
INT1	<---	INT	1.000			
INT2	<---	INT	1.014	.079	12.848	***
INT3	<---	INT	.828	.079	10.497	***
ATT1	<---	ATT	1.000			
ATT2	<---	ATT	1.230	.087	14.061	***

The Covariance between all the Latent variables are significant as P value is less than 0.05

Table 2: Correlation between the latent variables:

	Estimate
PEOU <--> PU	.719
PEOU <--> INT	.577
PEOU <--> ATT	.713
PU <--> INT	.607
PU <--> ATT	.700
INT <--> ATT	.612

There is a high positive correlation of 0.719 between PEOU and PU followed by PEOU and ATT at 0.713. The correlations between the other variables are given in the above table.

Based on Structure Equation Model using SPSS Amos 22 it is found that Chi-square (CMIN) = 61.812, Degree of freedom (DF) = 48 and probability level is about 0.000 which is evidence against the null hypothesis is not significant at the 0.05 level. CMIN/DF is called as the minimum discrepancy which is 1.288 Wheaton et al (1977) suggested that if the minimum discrepancy is less than 5 the model is reasonable fit.

The following value are found in our study for each parameter to test model fit

Table3: Parameter value for model fit measures with SPSS Amos

Name of the Parameter	Value
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	0.944
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.992
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0.042

Based on various studies conducted by Bentler and Bonett (1980), Jöreskog, and Sörbom (1996), Bollen's (1990) and Bentler (1980) it was suggested that if the Index value is greater than 0.9 and if RMSEA values is less than 0.05 it indicates model is fit and accepted.

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY TESTS

Table 4: Composite Reliability test:

	CR
PEOU	0.946
PU	0.909
INT	0.863
ATT	0.898

All the variables are having Composite Reliability greater than 0.7 which indicate there is a good Composite Reliability in the variables.

Table 5: Convergent Validity:

	AVE
PEOU	0.813
PU	0.768
INT	0.678
ATT	0.816

All the variables are having Convergent Validity greater than 0.5 which indicate there is good Convergent validity in the variables.

Table 6: Discriminant Validity:

	PEOU	PU	INT	ATT
PEOU	0.902			
PU	0.719	0.877		
INT	0.577	0.607	0.824	
ATT	0.713	0.7	0.612	0.903

The Discriminant value is greater than the corresponding correlation between the variables. Which indicate there is a good Discrimination between the factors in the analysis.

STRUCTURE EQUATION MODEL

SPSS Amos 22 software is used to perform confirmatory factor analysis using Structural Equation Model (SEM). The model is over-identified, a preferable situation for SEM.

Figure3: Structure Equation Model - The path diagram with standardized parameters estimate.

SPSS Amos Graphics has specified path-diagram in figure1 specifies the relationship between the observed variables. The portion of the model that specifies how the variables are related to each other is called structural model. The estimates with the largest value represent

the most important dimension in terms of its influence on dependent variables. The findings of the regression weights estimates are summarized in following table.

Table 7: Unstandardized Regression Weights Estimations

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
PU	<---	PEOU	.779	.080	9.751	***
ATT	<---	PEOU	.341	.081	4.213	***
ATT	<---	PU	.337	.073	4.587	***
INT	<---	PU	.224	.084	2.651	.008
INT	<---	ATT	.421	.109	3.859	***

P –value shows the significance of the estimation. If the P-value is less than 0.05 then, there is a significant effect of the independent variable on dependent variable (P-Values with *** indicate 0.000). All the Impacts are significant in this case.

Table 8: Standardized Regression Weights Estimations

			Estimate
PU	<---	PEOU	.722
ATT	<---	PEOU	.400
ATT	<---	PU	.427
INT	<---	PU	.282
INT	<---	ATT	.420

1. The Perceived Ease of Use has a significant impact of 0.722 on Perceived Usefulness.
2. The Perceived Ease of Use has a significant impact of 0.400 on Attitude to use multimedia.
3. The Perceived Usefulness has a significant impact of 0.427 in Attitude
4. The Perceived Usefulness has a significant impact of 0.282 in Behavioral Intention
5. The Attitude has a significant impact of 0.420 in Behavioral Intention

Based on Structure Equation Model using SPSS Amos 22 it is found that Chi-square (CMIN) = 67.425, Degree of freedom (DF) = 49 and probability level is about .041 which is evidence against the null hypothesis is not significant at the 0.05 level. CMIN/DF is called as the minimum discrepancy which is 1.376 Wheaton et al (1977) suggested that if the minimum discrepancy is less than 5 the model is reasonable fit.

The following value are found in our study for each parameter to test model fit.

Table 9: Parameter value for model fit measures with SPSS Amos

Name of the Parameter	Value
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	0.940
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.989
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0.047

Based on various studies conducted by Bentler and Bonett (1980), Jöreskog, and Sörbom (1996), Bollen's (1990) and Bentler (1980) it was suggested that if the Index value is greater than 0.9 and if RMSEA values is less than 0.08 it indicates model is fit and accepted.

Conclusion

There is a high positive correlation between Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU) followed by PEOU. The Perceived Ease of Use has a significant impact on Perceived Usefulness. The Perceived Ease of Use has a significant impact on Attitude to use multimedia. The Perceived Usefulness has a significant impact on Attitude. The Perceived Usefulness has a significant impact on Behavioral Intention. The Attitude has a significant impact on Behavioral Intention.

So based on the statistical analysis it is believed that the to influence the intention to use of multimedia if the multimedia materials are easy to use having relevance to self-learning, regional language use, user friendliness in accessing the functionalities.

We discovered that by utilizing multimedia teaching materials, we could more effectively promote teaching quality. However, with the rapid evolution of information technology and the rapid “out with the old and in with the new” of computer facilities, it is critical to encourage teachers to participate in teaching-related educational training.

The limitation of this study is the sampling method, as we used convenience sampling and restricted ourselves to Bengaluru Rural. Additional research can be conducted on larger samples of teachers at various levels of education in rural areas.

The authorities should consider to improve the ease with which multimedia materials can be applied and make it easier for teachers to create the materials. For instance, in establishing equipment for creating multimedia content and manpower to edit it. Teachers would provide the instructional content, while the additional manpower would construct the instructional materials. This would alleviate teachers' material development burdens and provide appropriate content for the class, thereby increasing ease of use and intention to use.

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